

THE STATUS OF DIGITAL CONTENT IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE ON THE INTERNET AND WAYS TO DEVELOP IT

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the current state of Uzbek-language digital content on the Internet, its expansion, relevance, and quality indicators. It also identifies factors that hinder the development of Uzbek-language content, and develops proposals and strategies for improvement.*

Keywords: *digital content, national content internet, ICT, development strategy, analysis, media.*

INTRODUCTION. In the 21st century, digital technologies are deeply embedded in almost every aspect of our lives. As a global source of information, the Internet has become not only a means of acquiring and disseminating knowledge, but also a platform for intercultural dialogue, promoting national values, and developing languages. Every people, every nation can become known worldwide through the presence of its language on the Internet, demonstrate its cultural wealth, and enrich the younger generation with national pride, historical memory, and modern knowledge.

The influence and presence of the state language - Uzbek - on the Internet is considered an important and urgent issue in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Today, the digital space is rich and comprehensive in content in English, Russian, Spanish, Chinese and other major languages, and users have wide opportunities. Unfortunately, the quantity and quality of content in the Uzbek language is currently insufficient. Many users are forced to turn to foreign languages when searching for information. This situation, in turn, negatively affects the position of the national language in the digital space.

Today, following the development of information technologies and Internet technologies in our country, various Internet portals and sites are being created and placed on the Internet for public use. These portals and sites have led to the development of digital content related to education. Following the increase in sites and portals in the .uz domain on the World Wide Web, many conveniences have been created for distance and online learners. The public educational information network of the Republic of Uzbekistan Ziyonet, established on September 28, 2005, was established. The main responsibility for creating the resources of the Ziyonet information and educational network is assigned to "the single integrator UZINFOCOM LLC".

The main goal of the Ziyonet network is to introduce a wide range of information and communication services for students in the education system. In addition to collecting the necessary information for young people, mentors, as well as all portal users, the Ziyonet network also undertakes the task of providing them with the necessary information in the field of information technologies, creating the necessary opportunities for mutual communication and exchange of experience.

According to the Ziyonet public information and education network, 5,455 interesting and useful websites for Internet users operate in our country. Of these, 3,380 are related to education and science, 230 to foreign languages, 580 to government agencies, 600 to the IT

industry, 516 to arts and culture, 220 to sports, 314 to business, 252 to news and media, 364 to entertainment, 255 to social spheres, 510 to medical, 373 to children, 26 to e-government portals, 107 to distance learning websites, and 521 to various other fields offer their services to users.

Out of a total of 3380 education and science websites, 623 are in the .uz domain. This is 18% of all education and science websites. As you can see, this figure is very low. The 3380 education and science websites mentioned above contain almost no websites related to a specific subject, such as language learning and programming, which is a very low figure [1].

Figure 1. Domain index of educational and science websites according to data from the Ziyonet public information and education network.

Therefore, the development of digital content in the Uzbek language on the Internet should be recognized not only as a part of language policy, but also as one of the main elements of the digital economy and information society. This article analyzes the current state of Uzbek content on the Internet, considers existing problems, and puts forward proposals for its development [2].

METHODOLOGY. This study used qualitative and quantitative analysis methods. It also used authoritative scientific articles, government reports, and open data from digital platforms to determine the state of digital content.

RESULTS. Among the various efforts being made to further develop the education sector in our country, the issue of increasing the number of websites on the global Internet in the state language and enriched with national content and maintaining them in a quality manner is also relevant. Unfortunately, today the level of content in the Uzbek language on the global Internet is not satisfactory [3].

This can also be seen from the following statistics:

According to the w3techs website, which summarizes information on web technologies worldwide, 49.1 percent of the information on the Internet is in English, 3.8 percent in Russian, and approximately 1.7 percent in Turkish [4].

However, there are also international languages that are more widely spoken around the world than Turkish. Table 1 below lists the 20 most common languages used in content creation.

Table 1.

No.	Language	Index (%)	No.	Language	Index (%)
1	English	49.1	11	Turkish	1.7
2	Spanish	6	12	Persia	1.2
3	German	5.8	13	China	1.1
4	Japanese	5.1	14	Vietnam	1.1
5	French	4.5	15	Indonesian	1.1
6	Portugal	3.9	16	Czech	1
7	Russian	3.8	17	Korean	0.8
8	Italian	2.8	18	Ukrainian	0.6
9	Dutch, Flemish	2.2	19	Hungarian	0.6
10	Polish	1.8	20	Arabic	0.5

Statistics on the use of content languages for websites

Compared to these indicators, materials in the Uzbek language, which make up less than 0.1 percent of the total information, rank 49th. This means that one in every thousand articles on the Internet is in Uzbek.

Research shows that the international open encyclopedia, Wikipedia, has more than 100,000 Uzbek materials. Most of these articles are copied from the "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan", and many articles are described very briefly. It is known that Wikipedia operates in more than 300 languages. There are separate encyclopedia articles in each language, and users can create content in their own language. English and Russian are also leading in the number of online encyclopedias on Wikipedia. Therefore, for those who want to get more information via the Internet, perfect knowledge of these two languages is required.

Looking at the above indicators, the state of Uzbek-language content on the Internet is not satisfactory. Although there is a state scientific publishing house "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan", the Uzbek-language materials on the Internet are not enough. Taking this into account, the gomus.info website was launched in our country. The site contains about 40 thousand articles, but this is not enough [5].

This raises a question: Why is there so much English content on the Internet? The following factors can be cited as an answer:

1. Global spread of English: English is one of the most widely spoken languages in the world, used as an official or second language in many countries. This increases the likelihood that content written in English will be understood by many users around the world.

2. Development of the Internet: Internet technologies were originally designed and developed in English. During the early 1990s, during the early development of the Internet, many websites, applications, and networks were created in English. Therefore, historically, there has been a lot of online resources and content in English.

3. Technology and science: Many technological and scientific news, articles, textbooks, and studies are written in English, as it is widely used in scientific and technical communication. English has also become the international language of communication for companies and researchers.

4. Countries influence: The United States and the United Kingdom are the countries that create the most content on the Internet. These countries are leaders in the production of technologies and the development of Internet resources. As a result, content created in English is widely used and distributed globally.

5. Global Business and Marketing: English is the primary language of communication for many international companies and businesses. These companies create their products, services, and promotional materials in English, which ensures that much of the internet content is in English.

Considering the above factors, not only state support, but also the general public and technological development are important for increasing Uzbek content. By creating useful platforms among users and using modern technologies, it is possible to increase the content in the Uzbek language. Also, creating high-quality resources in the Uzbek language and ensuring wide access to them will greatly contribute to the development of the language on a global scale.

Of course, presenting and using information in the Uzbek language on the Internet through a single platform is a difficult task. Because working with information related to different areas and different fields in one place also creates inconvenience for the user. However, by supplementing them with information related to the relevant fields on separate platforms, the scope of Uzbek-language content on the global network can be further increased. For example, the creation of separate high-quality websites for each of the subjects taught in educational institutions in our country can become one of the main reasons for the increase in Uzbek-language content on the Internet. In addition, through Uzbek information on these websites, users will have access to more and more understandable information [6].

Developing websites for each subject can have a positive impact on the increase in Uzbek content in the following ways:

1. Facilitating knowledge acquisition: Creating Uzbek-language websites for each subject will provide students and teachers with the opportunity to gain knowledge, stay up-to-date with new information, and access it anywhere. In addition, it will create ongoing resources for students and researchers through Uzbek-language scientific research, articles, educational materials, videos, and similar interactive content. This will increase the importance of the Uzbek language not only in the academic field, but also among the wider public.

2. Online education and training resources: By creating online education platforms for science, it will be possible to provide courses, textbooks, video lessons, and other educational materials in the Uzbek language. This creates a great opportunity for the wide distribution of Uzbek-language content.

3. Knowledge sharing: By creating websites for each discipline, experts, researchers, and academics will have the opportunity to share their knowledge with others. The amount of content in the Uzbek language will also increase through scientific journals, studies, and research in the Uzbek language.

4. Communication between local and global audiences: Websites on each subject can attract not only a local audience, but also a global audience. Users can share Uzbek content globally, learn about user opinions and exchange experiences. This helps to promote the global recognition of the Uzbek language and provides an impetus for the creation of new, modern content.

CONCLUSION. From the above information, it can be concluded that the development of websites on each topic will have a significant impact on the growth of Uzbek content. This is

important not only for improving the quality of scientific sources, but also for enriching the Uzbek language and popularizing it in the world. Increasing the content in the Uzbek language, in turn, ensures its further development and access to a wider audience.

In addition, the development of digital content in the Uzbek language on the Internet will not only ensure the preservation and enrichment of the language, but will also create the basis for the active participation of the Uzbek language in the digital economy. Therefore, the state, civil society and technology companies must work together to implement comprehensive strategies for the dissemination and development of digital content.

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